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Review Article

**THIAZOLIDINONE AS A LEAD COMPOUND IN DRUG
DISCOVERY- A REVIEW**Dhanya S^{1*}, Prasobh G R², Sheeja Rekha A G³, Athira A S⁴, E. Ajila⁵.¹Sree krishna college of pharmacy and research centre, Parassala, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala.

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Abstract:

Thiazolidinones and their derivatives are an important class of compounds in organic and medicinal chemistry. The 4-thiazolidinone ring system is a core structure in various synthetic pharmaceutical agents, displaying a broad spectrum of biological activities such as antitubercular, antibacterial, anti-HIV, anti-inflammatory, antimycobacterial, anticonvulsant, antihistaminic, anticancer and analgesic. This biologically active scaffold has encouraged interest in synthesizing several new compounds by attaching 4- thiazolidinone moieties.

Key words: Thiazolidinones, Anticancer, Antitubercular.

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INTRODUCTION:

Thiazolidinone, a saturated form of thiazole with carbonyl group on 4th carbon, has been considered as a magic moiety which poses almost all types of biological activities. Tetrahydro derivative of thiazole is known as thiazolidine and the oxo derivative of thiazolidine is known as thiazolidinones.

Substitution is possible at 2,3 and 5 positions. Various optical and geometrical isomers are reported. A series of regioselective isomers has been reported in some

works. The carbonyl group of 4-thiazolidinone is highly unreactive. But in few cases 4-thiazolidinone on reaction with Lawesson's reagent gives corresponding 4-thione derivatives.

Thiazolidinones are known to exhibit antitubercular, antibacterial, anticonvulsant, antifungal and antithyroid activities. Some of thiazolidine derivatives were found to show interesting anti-HIV and anticancer activities.

Thiazolidinone general structure**Chemistry**

IUPAC name: 1,3-thiazolidine-4-one

Empirical formula: C₃H₅NOS

Chemical structure:

Physical property: Solids, often melting with decomposition, soluble in water.

Molecular weight: 103.14g/mol

Synthesis of Thiazolidinones:

Several methods for synthesis of 4-thiazolidinone are available in literature which involve conventional one pot, two pot synthesis, and microwave as well as combinatorial synthesis method.

▪ *Ashok Kumar et al.* synthesized N-(6-bromo-2-methyl-4-oxoquinazolin-3(4H)-yl)-2-(4-(2-(substituted phenyl)-4-oxothiazolidin-3-yl)-5-(pyridine-4-yl)3-thio) acetamido-1,2,4-triazoles by the reaction of compounds 6-bromo-2-methyl-4-

oxoquinazolin-3(4H)-yl-2-(4-(substituted benzylideneamino)-5-(pyridine)3thio) acetamido-1,2,4-triazoles with thioglycolic acid in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride. All the newly synthesized compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *P. vulgaris*, *K. pneumoniae*. Structures of all the compounds were established by elemental and spectral (IR, ¹H NMR and Mass) analysis. (*Ashok Kumar et al., 2010*)

- *Yadav D Bodke et al.*, synthesized 2-oxo-N-(4-oxo-2-substituted phenyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-3-yl-2H-chromene-3-carboxamide by refluxing Schiff's bases with mercapto acetic acid. (*Yadav D Bodke et al.*, **2010**)

- *S. Jubie et al.* synthesized a new series of 3-(methoxy phenyl)-2-aryl thiazolidine-4-one by the reaction of Schiff bases of 4-methoxy aniline with mercapto acetic acid. The synthesized compounds were screened for antitubercular, antimicrobial and cytotoxicity studies. (*S. Jubie et al.*, **2009**)

Microwave method of Synthesis

A mixture of rhodanine (20mmol), respective aromatic aldehyde (20mmol) and $\text{NH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{NH}_4$ was subjected to Microwave irradiation at 600watt intermittently at 30 second interval for specific time (3-6minutes). (Srinivas M. et al., 2013)

SOME NEW LEAD IN QUINAZOLINONE DISCOVERY

Thiazolidine as Anticancer Agents³

□ Dmytro Havrylyuk et al., 2011, synthesized and carried out antitumor activity by screening of novel isatin based conjugates with thiazolidine and pyrazoline. The synthesized compounds were tested for their anticancer activity in NCI60 cell lines. (Dmytro Havrylyuk et al., 2011)

□ Qianbin Li et al., 2010 identified thiazolidine-2,4-dione derivative, 3-(2- aminoethyl)-5-(3-phenyl-propylidene)-thiazolidine-2,4-dione as a dual inhibitor of the Raf/MEK/ extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK) and the phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI3K)/Akt signaling cascades. The discovered compound inhibited cell proliferation, induced early apoptosis, and arrested cells in G0/G1 phase in human leukemia U937 cells. These results indicate its potential as a new lead compound to develop novel dual signaling pathway inhibitors and anticancer agents. (Qianbin Li et al., 2010)

Thiazolidine as Antitubercular Agents⁴

- Himaja Malipeddi et al. synthesized a series of novel thiazolidinones by cyclocondensation of various Schiff bases of amino thiadiazole with thioglycolic acid. Docking studies were carried out for the synthesized compounds which were also evaluated for in-vitro anti-tubercular activity at a concentration of 0.1 – 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ by Micro plate Blue Alamar Assay method. (Himaja Malipeddi., 2012).

- Samadhiya P. et al synthesized new series of N-[(3-1H-6-nitroindazol-1-yl)- propyl] -2-(substituted phenyl)-4-oxo-5-(substituted benzylidene)-1, 3 thiazolidine -carboxamide, and all these synthesized compounds were screened for their antitubercular activities. (Samadhiya p. et al., 2012)
- S.Jubie et al., 2009 synthesized a new series of 3-(methoxyphenyl)-2-aryl thiazolidine-4-one by the reaction of Schiff bases of 4-methoxy aniline with mercaptoacetic acid. The synthesized compounds were screened for antitubercular, antimicrobial and cytotoxicity studies. (S.Jubie et al., 2009)

THIAZOLIDINE AS ANTIMICROBIAL AGENT [5]:

- N C Desai and coworkers synthesized a series of N-{5-[(2-chlorophenyl) methylene]-2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4-oxo (1, 3-thiazolidin-3-yl)} {4-[2-(4-methyl phenyl)-4-oxo (3-hydroquinazolin-yl)] phenyl} carboxamides . All these synthesized compounds were screened for in vitro antibacterial and antifungal activities. (N C Desai et al., 2012)
- B.K Manuprasad described a facile synthesis of novel 1, 3-thiazolidine purine nucleosides from L-Cystein methylester hydrochloride. This was reported for their antibacterial activity. (B.K Manuprasad et al., 2011).

W. El Sayed et al. synthesized a number of new disubstituted 2, 5-thiazolidinone derivatives and tested for their antimicrobial activity against *Bacillus subtilis* (Gram-positive), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Gram negative), and *Streptomyces* species (Actinomycetes). (W.El Sayed et al., 2009)

THIAZOLIDINE AS ANTIOXIDANT:

A series of Schiff's bases (E)-N-2-aryliden-2-(4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-chromen-7- yloxy) acetohydrazides 2a-l and N-(2-(substituted phenyl)-4-oxo-thiazolidin-3- yl)-2-(4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-chromen-7-yloxy) acetamides were synthesized and evaluated for their antioxidant activity by the phosphomolybdenum method. (Cacić et al., 2010)

THIAZOLIDINE SUBSTITUTED QUINAZOLINE AS ANTICANCER AGENT:

- Safinaz et al prepared 2, 3-disubstituted-4(3H) quinazolinone derivatives and these compounds have been tested for cytotoxic activity against human mammary carcinoma cell line (MCF7) using doxorubicin as a reference standard. (Safinaz E.et al., 2010)

CONCLUSION:

Thiazolidinones are known to exhibit antitubercular, antibacterial, anticonvulsant, antifungal and antithyroid activities. Some of thiazolidine derivatives were found to show interesting anti-HIV and anticancer activities.

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